

RESEARCH REPORT
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Safe and Inclusive Work Environment Plan

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TREPA

**Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals**

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

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STATEMENT

As a project advocating for intersectionality across a diverse range of conservation issues, **TREPA** (Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals) also considers intersectionality across people's identities. Therefore, the TREPA project firmly abides by the following principles:

- We value diversity, equity, inclusion, and social justice (“**DEIJ**”) as core principles.
- We therefore strive to provide a safe, inclusive, diverse, and respectful work environment for our team members and the people we interact with, regardless of their race, ethnicity, gender, religion, sexual orientation, ability, age, or any other aspect of their identity.
- We acknowledge that systemic discrimination and oppression have historically affected certain groups of people, and we are committed to ensuring that our work confronts these issues.
- We encourage addressing unconscious bias and promoting inclusive language.
- We recognize the importance of local knowledge and Indigenous Knowledge Systems, strive to empower Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and are committed to including their perspectives in our work.
- We believe in the power of transdisciplinary and collective contribution spaces where everyone can develop to their fullest capacity as they desire. This translates into promoting dialogue, knowledge sharing, mentoring, and mutual support.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT

TREPA is a research project, funded with federal funds from the United States of America, that seeks to advance and enable cooperative research and health security with global partners by exploring how wildlife trafficking and associated illicit supply chains involve both overt and covert human behaviors that create new spaces, reservoirs, exposure pathways, and transmission routes for zoonotic pathogens of security concern and pandemic potential such as anthrax. Knowledge accrued through this research will help fill essential knowledge gaps about animal-pathogen-biothreat networks that exist because wildlife trafficking provides a clear, yet uncharted, opportunity for an unintentional incursion of a pathogen that knows no natural borders.

TREPA's objectives are to: 1) assess existing SB&S efforts and detection networks for illegal wildlife trade (IWT) and anthrax using the One Health approach; 2) level set datasets with novel insight about wildlife trafficking, anthrax transmission, animal behavior, and use of wildlife such as in traditional medicine; 3) design operations research and location science-based surveillance and response models to leverage existing and sustain new capacity, technology, and health systems; 4) harmonize a sustainable 'network of networks' to promote joint SB&S efforts that encourage timely reporting, emerging disease detection, and outbreak response.

To attain its objectives, TREPA will undertake research through a variety of methods. These will encompass desk-based research, on-site visits to evaluate the capacities of laboratories, animal tagging and monitoring, processing and testing lab samples, and conducting face-to-face interviews, participatory mapping, and social network analyses in South Africa and Mozambique.

TREPA brings together a diverse group of people, including at least European, North American, Southern African, and South American scholars, professionals, and traditional healers. This project will be led by the University of Maryland, College Park ("**UMD**"), as the main recipient of the award. Yet, all team members are fundamental for its successful execution.

OFF-SITE RESEARCH SETTINGS

1. Fieldwork Settings

Fieldwork, the process of observing and collecting data about people, cultures, and natural environments outside the designated worksite (e.g., home office, University lab), conducted for TREPA will occur in different settings, depending on the tasks to be conducted. The team members working on tagging and monitoring vultures and human dimensions in South Africa and Mozambique will mainly face rural and sub-urban settings with limited access to the internet and electricity, as well as power outages. At times, team members will need to drive back and forth from South Africa to Mozambique in shared car drives. These will mainly be road trips, most likely crossing the border via Kruger National Park or via the Ressano Garcia immigration post. Accommodations may be shared during these trips if team members feel comfortable and freely decide to. Team members who do not want to share accommodations can have individual lodging accommodations and should work within budgets. See the names of the individuals who will be part of these trips in Appendix 1. Questions about budgets can be directed to UMD at nmunozc@umd.edu.

The team members in charge of assessing the laboratories' capacities will travel mostly to urban and sub-urban areas in South Africa and Mozambique, some of which might have power outages at unannounced intervals. On regular occasions, they may need to travel to more rural areas with limited access to internet, power, and cellular service. UMD has an emergency satellite phone that can be signed out as available at no charge to the TREPA team. Trips between cities or towns will be carried out in either shared or individual car drives. TREPA strongly encourages team members to take the environmental footprint of their travel choices into account, thus promoting, when feasible, the less impactful option. See the names of the individuals that will be part of these trips in Appendix 1.

Some of the challenges the team may encounter while in the field are:

- New, unfamiliar, unknown, or nonexistent rules of conduct and reporting mechanisms.

- Unknown languages and difficulty to communicate.
- Reduced independence for access to transportation, food, medical resources, etc.
- Distance from personal support networks at home.
- Unfamiliar road infrastructure (e.g., tar and dust roads), unfamiliar driving and traffic rules.
- Unfamiliar cultural norms, including food, bathrooms, personal space, and speaking volume.
- Long days with physically and psychologically strenuous work and exhaustion.
- Exposure to harsh environmental conditions and potential greater risk of environmental hazards or unfamiliar risks.

In certain occasions, impacts from these challenges may persist beyond fieldwork, and team members are encouraged to raise these issues to other team members or to UMD to find ways to address them.

2. Indaba Settings

TREPA foresees hosting two policymakers' events called 'Indaba' during the course of the project. The first Indaba will take place during Year 1 (2023), and the second will take place in Year 5 (2027).

TREPA's 2023 Indaba will take place at the Southern African Wildlife College (**SAWC**) in Hoedspruit, South Africa, between September 6-10, 2023. The purpose of this event is to co-design the project and promote networking. This Indaba aims to bring together a diverse audience to clarify opportunities and challenges associated with:

- (I) A surveillance sample management system for enhanced diagnostic efficiency in collaboration with diverse and local partners that can help establish new or link existing surveillance networks, outbreak analysis, and risk mitigation strategies;

- (II) Novel analytical tools and decision support models that can enhance self-directed local livelihoods by addressing monitoring, detection, prevention, interdiction, and remediation;
- (III) Enhanced capacity to promote joint SB&S efforts that can encourage improved human and animal health, timely reporting, emerging disease detection and outbreak response; and
- (IV) Enhanced monitoring of wildlife trade and supply chains across the heterogeneous contexts within which they occur.

The SAWC is located 60km outside Hoedspruit and is accessible via a paved road. The nearest airport is located at Hoedspruit, but shuttles will also be made available for guests arriving at Hoedspruit Eastgate Airport. SAWC offers accommodation to TREPA's team and guests, making available 57 twin rooms.

The SAWC will make its facilities available to TREPA for the 2023 Indaba to host presentations, individual meetings, and engagement-based activities. It will also be able to provide transportation to nearby reserves or national parks to participate in experiential learning activities.

Although the location of the 2027 Indaba is yet unknown, previously discussed considerations shall also be applicable to this event.

Participants to the Indaba can find information on what to expect at SAWC and what to pack [here](#).

3. Nurturing a safe and inclusive environment

3.1 General Provisions

TREPA invites its members to take an active role in nurturing a safe and inclusive environment. To support and guide these efforts, TREPA will work to:

- Encourage team members to enroll in any training available at their organizations on promoting DEIJ and preventing discrimination and harassment.
- Promote open verbal and written communication and active listening among all team members and people interacting with TREPA. Team members can also request their comments/feedback to remain anonymous.
- Provide a welcoming space for team members to suggest decision-making processes.
- Foster a sense of belonging and empowerment by allowing team members to participate in proposing activities, study design, and decision-making.
- Invite team members to determine a group code of conduct.
- Promote mentor/mentee mechanisms among team members.
- Collect lessons learned and record any situations that relate to this SIWE Plan.

To protect physical integrity and security for team members, TREPA will work to:

- Provide a checklist that ensures physical, psychological, social, economic, and other safety and belonging during fieldwork.
- Urge team members to read and sign the checklist and reevaluate of the code of conduct on an annual basis.
- Provide resources/staff that can facilitate discussions on DEIJ and security.
- Encourage team members to establish support mechanisms for fieldwork, such as regular check-ins with other team members or with the institution/organization they belong to.

TREPA invites team members to inform UMD, if their respective institution does not offer any training on maintaining responsible conduct in research and/or trainings on DEIJ. This notification will allow UMD to guide team members on available training resources. It would be desirable that team members inform UMD about the completed pieces of training that support these goals.

TREPA welcomes any team members to send their proposals, suggestions, comments, and feedback to UMD regarding the adoption of a group code of conduct and a decision-making process. Overall, all team members are encouraged to participate in all activities and provide any feedback to UMD.

Any such notices or feedback should be addressed to the Principal Investigator, Meredith L. Gore (gorem@umd.edu), and/or Natalia Muñoz Cassolis (nmunozc@umd.edu). Feedback will be initially discussed within UMD's team members and will be shared with all team members on a confidential basis.

Upon receiving the proposals about the group code of conduct and/or decision-making process, UMD will invite team members to volunteer in a task force specifically designed to foster discussions around these topics and advance their adoption as part of the project. Adopted decisions will be shared with all team members via email, and the resulting code of conduct and/or process for decision-making will be uploaded to TREPA's Google Drive, where all team members can access it.

3.2 Indaba provisions

TREPA encourages its team members to:

- Promote diversity among participants, our speaker lineup, and workshop facilitators.
- Encourage participants to adhere to and abide by TREPA's statement provided in Section I.

- Provide training on DEIJ for all conference staff. See some available resources here: <https://diversity.umd.edu/>
- Foster a safe environment where participants and team members can freely engage in respectful conversations, dialogues, or discussions.
- Stress to participants the importance of not sharing any personal identifying information from fellow participants without their express written consent.
- Guarantee that the DEIJ Facilitators (as defined below) attend the Indaba.

4. Communication and Delegation Processes during Fieldwork / Indaba

All team members should plan fieldwork in advance and check any specific equipment requirements including but not limited to, the appropriate shoe ware and clothing, maps, first aid kits, required medications (e.g., for allergies, tropical infectious diseases, etc.), sunscreen and sun protections, glasses and lenses, and comply with specific requirements to travel with laptops or other devices (e.g., bringing adapters, power banks, etc.). An indicative guidance on planning your fieldwork can be found [here](#). As part of the planning, team members participating in fieldwork should also disclose any important allergies or medical conditions that may require immediate assistance from other team members (e.g., epilepsy, EpiPen for allergies).

During fieldwork or the Indaba events, at least two team members from different institutions shall have a mobile phone with roaming. All team members should be aware that they can freely access these mobile phones for regular check-ins and for reporting any misconduct. UMD personnel shall always make use of the UMD satellite phone when engaging in fieldwork, and such phone shall always be freely accessible to all team members for regular check-ins if no other communication means are available.

Team members and collaborators will share phone numbers between staff/demonstrators. A group chat (e.g., WhatsApp) may be established.

Staff/Demonstrator roles will be designated, including:

- Field lead - logistics (keeping to time, coordinating with coach drivers, accommodation personnel, etc.)
- First aid lead (in charge of first aid kits)
- Someone in charge of documents -handouts, guides, assessment paperwork, student feedback forms
- All staff designated as 'safe persons' for anyone to report concerns.
- Follow-up process will be set in place and known to all.
- At least two members of staff/demonstrators to be alcohol-free 24 hours a day on a rota basis (or similar). At least one will be a driver. Zero-tolerance for alcohol and drugs policy for designated drivers.

5. Emergency Assistance

Team members should check their institution's emergency assistance protocols and phone numbers before engaging in fieldwork. Any institutional hotline numbers or emergency contact numbers, as well as personal emergency contacts, should be made available to other team members on the first day of fieldwork. UMD personnel can check these resources [here](#).

When conducting fieldwork overseas for prolonged periods of time, team members are encouraged to contact their consulate office and notify that they are in-country.

6. Guidelines for complaints or reports

TREPA will train at least 2 team members on DEIJ to facilitate and receive any reports, events, and complaints of DEIJ violations, discrimination, and/or harassment (hereinafter the “**DEIJ Facilitators**”). Some examples of DEIJ violations include abuse of any person, but not limited to, harassment, stalking, bullying, or hazing of any kind, whether the behavior is carried out verbally, physically, electronically, or in written form. It will also include any unwelcome, offensive, indecent, obscene, or disorderly conduct.

The team of DEIJ facilitators will ideally have gender and nationality diversity. It is advisable not to appoint team members in high leadership positions as DEIJ Facilitators to avoid any fear or apprehension in reporting.

UMD's DEIJ policy applies to all students, staff, visitors, trainees, volunteers, applicants, vendors and contractors. Thus, DEIJ Facilitators shall inform UMD's Office of Civil Rights and Sexual Misconduct about any violation via email (titleixcoordinator@umd.edu) or by submitting an online report at [https://ocrsm.umd.edu/file-report within 90 business days of the incident](https://ocrsm.umd.edu/file-report_within_90_business_days_of_the_incident). UMD shall not be held liable in any respect for any violation involving staff or personnel from other institutions or organizations that do not fall within UMD's policy. Yet, DEIJ Facilitators can ask UMD's personnel for support in requesting an investigation and/or holding the third-party institution or entity liable.

7. Access to SIWE Plan

A draft of the SIWE Plan will be shared with all TREPA members for review and feedback. It shall, later on, be approved by TREPA members in a regular team meeting, and UMD shall share its adopted version with all team members via email. Upon approval, the SIWE Plan must be translated into Portuguese. The SIWE Plan shall also be available on TREPA's Google Drive. It shall be made publicly available for consultation of all Indaba participants via its publication on a website, and a link shall be included in the invitations to the Indaba.